

FATIGUE DAMAGE ANALYSIS OF NOTCHED CARBON/EPOXY LAMINATES BY THERMOELASTIC EMISSION AND THREE DIMENSIONAL FINITE ELEMENT METHODS

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ABSTRACT

Three dimensional crack propagation in a notched carbon/epoxy (90/0)_{2s} laminate is analyzed by using a finite element method. The numerical results indicate that the transverse crack in the 90° layer propagates in the stable manner. Extension of fatigue damages is investigated by using thermoelastic technique (SPATE). Initiation and growth of the transverse cracks in the surface ply can be detected clearly in the thermoelastic stress patterns. The combined numerical and experimental analyses indicate that K_{max} is nearly constant at the near threshold condition. A damage-threshold approach is proposed based on three dimensional finite element analysis and linear elastic fracture mechanics.

INTRODUCTION

A damage-threshold/Fail-safety approach has been proposed¹ for ensuring that composite structures are sufficiently durable in the normal operating condition, as well as adequately fail-safe for safety. Three dimensional approach may be necessary for fracture analysis of composite laminates because the fracture processes, for example, matrix cracking and delamination, are three dimensional. Finite element method may be a powerful tool. A method of stress pattern analysis by thermal emission (SPATE) has been developed² based on the thermoelastic effect. The method has been successfully applied to carbon composites by authors³. When fatigue damages accumulate in the composites, they may change the stress distribution. In the present paper, the combined numerical and thermoelastic techniques are applied to fatigue damage analysis of notched carbon/epoxy laminates within the framework of Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics.

THERMOELASTIC STRESS ANALYSIS

1. Principle

When elastic body is compressed and expanded adiabatically, the temperature increases and decreases, respectively, due to the thermoelastic interaction. Cyclic load is applied to the

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body under the adiabatic condition, and the temperature change is detected with exactly the same frequency of the applied load. Stress patterns are obtained as the temperature distribution by scanning on the surface of the body.

2. Thermoelastic Effect of Orthotropic Plate

Thermoelastic effect of orthotropic plate has been investigated by authors³, and a linear relation is obtained between the temperature change, ΔT , and the change of the longitudinal and transverse stresses, $\Delta\sigma_L$ and $\Delta\sigma_T$, respectively.

$$\Delta T = -\frac{T}{\rho C_\sigma} (\alpha_L \Delta\sigma_L + \alpha_T \Delta\sigma_T) \quad (1)$$

Where, T is the absolute temperature, ρ is the density, and C_σ is the specific heat at constant stress. α_L and α_T are the thermal expansion coefficients in the longitudinal and transverse directions, respectively.

In the case of an unidirectionally reinforced carbon/epoxy lamina, α_T is much larger than α_L in the absolute value. Consequently, the first term in the parentheses can be neglected.

$$\Delta T = -K_m \cdot T \cdot \Delta\sigma_T, \quad K_m = \frac{\alpha_T}{\rho C_\sigma} \quad (2)$$

K_m is the thermoelastic constant. Eq. (2) indicates that the component of transverse stress can be detected by using the thermoelastic technique in the case of carbon composites.

3. SPATE System

Thermal emission from specimen is detected and analyzed by SPATE. Data acquisition is under computer control and scans are produced in a raster-like manner as shown in Fig. 1. Stress detail to 0.5 mm dimension is resolvable. A correlation technique has achieved extremely high detection sensitivity of temperature². The resolution of temperature is 0.001 K.

The thermoelastic constant, K_m , of the unidirectionally reinforced carbon/epoxy lamina is $2.5 \times 10^{-11} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$ (Ref. 2), and the value is about seven times larger than steel. The sensitivity of 0.001 K is equivalent to stress of 0.14 MPa.

Fig. 1 SPATE system

THREE DIMENSIONAL FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

A three dimensional finite element code for a super computer (CRAY X-MP/216) has been developed and applied to fatigue damage analysis of composite laminates because the fracture processes of delamination and transverse lamina cracking are essentially three

Fig. 2 Finite element model of lamina cracking

Fig. 3 Mesh patterns of finite element model

Fig. 4 Change of stress intensity factor with transverse crack growth

dimensional. An isoparametric element with 20 nodes and a singular element⁴ of crack tip are used for the analysis.

Transverse cracks, which propagate from a circular notch in a (90/0)_{2s} carbon/epoxy laminate, are analyzed in the present paper. Lamina cracking is modeled as shown in Fig. 2, and three dimensional stress intensity factor of the transverse crack is calculated from the

intensity of stress singularity in the crack tip element. Mesh patterns of the finite element models are shown in Fig. 3.

Numerical results of K_I of a propagating transverse crack in the surface lamina is shown in Fig. 4. K_I decreases with the crack propagation under fixed load condition, and thus the transverse crack growth is stable.

EXPERIMENTS

1. Material and Specimen

Material tested is carbon/epoxy (90/0)_{2s} laminate which is made from Toray P305 prepregs (T300/#2500). The nominal thickness of the lamina and laminate are 0.25 mm and 2.0 mm, respectively. The nominal fiber volume fraction is 60 %. Tensile coupons with circular hole are machined as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Notched tension specimen

2. Test Method

The specimen was mounted in a test frame by using wedge action tension grips, and tension-tension cyclic load is applied to it by an electrohydraulic testing machine. The load frequency was 10 Hz, which satisfy the adiabatic condition. The ratio of minimum and maximum loads, R , was chosen to be 0.1 and kept constant during the test. The extension of fatigue damages was investigated by SPATE during the test.

Fig. 6 S N diagram of notched (90/0) laminates

RESULTS

S-N curve is shown in Fig. 6. The maximum stress, σ_{max} , is measured as the average stress on the unnotched ligament area, that is, $\sigma_{max} = P_{max}/[B(W-d)]$. The fatigue strength, σ_f , at $N=10^7$ reaches 450 MPa, which is about 70% of the static strength, though transverse

cracks are detected by SPATE at σ_{\max} of 70 MPa. As transverse cracking is stable, the cracks propagate with increasing the applied load. The load history is shown in Fig. 7. Points indicated by symbol (\bullet) represent the near threshold levels, at which the transverse crack growth can not be detected by SPATE.

Fig.7 History of fatigue loading

(a) Before fatigue test

(d) $\sigma_{\max} = 145$ MPa

(b) $\sigma_{\max} = 94$ MPa

(c) $\sigma_{\max} = 123$ MPa

(e) $\sigma_{\max} = 203$ MPa

Fig. 8 Thermoelastic stress patterns of fatigue damages from circular notch

Fig. 9 Change of K_{max} with crack growth at near threshold condition

Thermoelastic stress patterns at the near threshold level are shown Figs. 8 (a)-(e). The transverse cracks on the surface lamina can be clearly detected as the unstressed regions. The crack length is measured from the thermoelastic stress patterns, and K_{max} is calculated from Fig. 4. A relation between K_{max} and the crack length is shown in Fig. 9. K_{max} slightly increases with crack growth. We think it is due to effect of average stress for small crack. K_{max} is nearly constant for larger crack. The average value of all data points is 0.82 MPa√m.

If we assume an allowable crack length is 5 mm, the fatigue strength of the specimen can be calculated to be 141 MPa from Figs. 4 and 9. The value indicates the fatigue design strength based on the damage-threshold concept.

CONCLUSIONS

Three dimensional crack propagation in a notched carbon/epoxy (90/0)_{2s} laminates has been analyzed numerically by using a finite element method. The numerical results indicate that the transverse crack in the 90° layer propagates in the stable manner, that is, the stress intensity factor decreases with crack growth under the constant load condition.

The extension of fatigue damages has been investigated experimentally by using a method of thermoelastic stress pattern analysis (SPATE). The initiation and growth of the transverse cracks in the surface ply can be detected with very high accuracy by using the thermoelastic technique, and it is confirmed experimentally that the transverse crack growth is stable.

The combined numerical and experimental analyses indicate that K_{max} is nearly constant at the near threshold condition. A damage-threshold approach has been proposed based on the three dimensional finite element analysis and the concept of fatigue threshold.

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